

VITAMIN D AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN THE COURSE OF COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN

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Annotation. *Global epidemiological studies confirm that vitamin D deficiency may lead to an increased risk of influenza and respiratory tract infections. The purpose of our study was to study the characteristics of the influence and significance of vitamin D deficiency in young children with community-acquired pneumonia. The level of vitamin D plays an important role in the course, severity and unfavorable outcome of CAP in young children, which deserves special attention and requires a more in-depth analysis in the diagnosis, prevention and treatment of diseases of the bronchopulmonary system in children.*

Keywords: *children, Pneumonia, Vitamin D.*

Relevance. Despite the improvement of preventive measures, community-acquired pneumonia remains one of the most common infections associated with medical care and the most common infectious complication in the intensive care unit [3]. Respiratory diseases occupy the first place in the structure of the general morbidity, accounting for almost 60.0%. Among the causes of death in children, bronchopulmonary diseases are in 3rd place after external factors (trauma and poisoning) and malformations, while pneumonia occupies the largest share [2,5]. Despite successes in treatment and diagnosis, acute pneumonia remains an urgent problem, due to the increasing frequency of prolonged course and adverse outcomes diseases. Pneumonia is the leading cause of death in children worldwide. In recent years, the effect of vitamin D on immunity and inflammation has been actively studied [1-3]. Today, the role of vitamin D for children and adults is of great importance. Global epidemiological studies confirm that vitamin D deficiency can lead to an increased risk of influenza and respiratory tract infections. In clinical practice, an increase in the incidence of acute respiratory diseases is observed in both newborns and older children with insufficient vitamin D levels [2]. Some studies conducted in the USA in 2019 show that newborns with lower serum vitamin D levels are more susceptible to cases of acute nasopharyngitis[3], lower respiratory tract infections and MS-associated bronchiolitis, pneumonia. Another study conducted in Norway 2020 revealed a reduction in the risk of lower respiratory tract infections, including pneumonia during the first 3 years of life in those children whose mothers are in the 2nd trimester of pregnancy they had a higher serum level of 25-hydroxycholecalciferol [3]. Fairchok M. et al. (2017) in a scientific paper also provides data on the relationship between low serum levels of 25-OH vitamin D and the frequency of respiratory diseases, bronchitis, pneumonia. The study involved 90 patients with acute respiratory infection (ARI), the main causative agent of which was the MS virus. In 66% of cases, the serum level of 25-hydroxycalciferol in the observed patients was below 30 mg/ml (main group). The duration of hospitalization and the use of additional oxygenation were significantly higher in the main group compared with patients in the control group with normal serum levels of 25-OH vitamin D. The authors also proved the connection between 25-hydroxycalciferol deficiency and predominantly breastfeeding of newborns [2,3,7]. A prospective study of 743 Canadian children aged 3 to 15 years also revealed a correlation between lower serum vitamin D levels (25-OH) and indicators of laboratory-confirmed viral infection of the respiratory tract [4]. Convincing evidence of the effect of vitamin D on reducing the risk of viral respiratory infection was obtained in prospective studies

of preventive vitamin D administration [2,6,8]. Grant C.C. et al. (2015) demonstrated a decrease in the number of first aid for acute respiratory infections among New Zealand newborns receiving prophylactically high doses of vitamin D, and whose mothers also received vitamin D during pregnancy [7]. Goodall E.C. et al. (2014) also found a decrease in laboratory-specified upper respiratory tract viral infections and viral load in Canadian adults receiving vitamin D₃ [2]. Another study convincingly demonstrated a decrease in morbidity in Swedish adult patients with frequent respiratory infections treated with vitamin D₃ prophylaxis [2]. In addition, there is evidence that vitamin D deficiency is associated with the development of diseases associated with the influenza virus type A. It has been proven that children receiving vitamin D supplements have a 2-fold lower risk of getting the flu compared with children not receiving vitamin D preparations - 10 and 19%, respectively (p=0.04) [7-9].

Based on the conducted literature research data and the relevance of the effect of vitamin D deficiency on the development of infectious diseases in children of various ages, it is presumably a risk factor in the occurrence of acute respiratory infections and various respiratory pathologies and contributes to their severity.

Aim. To study the features of the effect and significance of vitamin D deficiency in young children with community-acquired pneumonia.

Research materials and methods. All children underwent clinical and anamnestic (complaints, medical history and objective data) examination methods, instrumental (chest X-ray, peak flowmetry (according to indications, depending on age), pulse oximetry, ECG, conventional laboratory tests. The level of serum vitamin D (VD) was studied in 50 children aged 1 to 3 years, patients with community-acquired pneumonia (VP). VD deficiency was defined as a concentration of 25(OH)Serum D is <20 ng/ml, deficiency is from 20 to 30 and the norm is from 30 to 100 ng/ml.

Results. The results indicate that the vitamin D level in 30.4% of children was normal (>50 ng/ml), in 45.2% of children - insufficiency, in 14.8% of children - deficiency of VD. The level provides protection against infection due to genes whose work is regulated by 25(OH)D₃, as shown in Fig.1.

Figure 1. Indicators of the frequency of vitamin D

In children in the group with insufficiency and deficiency of VD, severe course of VP was noted, hyperthermic syndrome - febrile temperature persisted for 3 days or more in 45.5% of patients, subfebrile temperature was noted in 54.5% of patients. The severity of pneumonia in children was significantly influenced by an unfavorable premorbid background and concomitant pathology of the body. Another clinical manifestation of pneumonia was a wet cough. Patients with insufficiency or deficiency of VD complained of productive cough in 76% of cases, and dry cough in 22.7%. Dry cough was significantly more common in children aged 2-3 years, and

productive cough was more common in children aged 1 year. Children complained of decreased appetite, weakness and fatigue in 62% of cases, whereas 38% of children with normal vitamin D levels had mild complaints. Inspiratory dyspnea was observed in children with vitamin D deficiency or deficiency (77.8%), in other children - mixed dyspnea, shown in table 1

Table 1. Clinic of community-acquired pneumonia depending on vitamin D(%)

Signs	Attribute	Insufficiency and deficiency VD	Normal VD
Asthenovegetative syndrome	Decreased appetite	21	15
	weakness	30	11,2
	fatigue	11	11,8
Temperature	febrile	45,5	54,5
	low-grade fever	54,5	45,5
Cough	productive	76,0	28,0
	dry	22,7	17,3
Dyspnea	inspiratory	77,8	22,2
	mixed	22,2	-
Cough	productive	76,0	28,0
	dry	22,7	17,3
Dyspnea	inspiratory	77,8	22,2
	mixed	22,2	-

The results indicate that the vitamin D level in 40% of children was normal (>50 ng/ml), in 45.2% of children - insufficiency, in 14.8% of children - deficiency of VD. According to the literature, the level of VD provides protection against infection due to genes whose work is regulated by 25(OH)D3. In children in the group with insufficiency and deficiency of VD, severe course of VP was noted, hyperthermic syndrome - febrile temperature persisted for 3 or more days in 45.5% of patients, subfebrile temperature was noted in 54.5% of patients (Table No. 1). The main complaints were productive cough in patients with insufficiency or insufficiency of VD - in 76% of cases, dry cough - in 22.7%. Chest percussion revealed a shortening of the pulmonary sound. An important diagnostic sign of focal pneumonia was the characteristic clinical picture in the lungs: persistent local small-bubble wheezing and crepitation were heard against the background of hard breathing. Chest X-ray was performed in all examined patients, while homogeneous infiltrative shadows were detected in the form of foci of various sizes. The lowest rates of anemia of the 2nd degree were in children with vitamin D deficiency and deficiency, which amounted to 78.6%, and anemia of the 1st degree was in children with normal vitamin activity - 5.6%. The most common was high leukocytosis with a shift of the formula to the left, toxic granularity of neutrophils. A number of patients showed leukopenia with a shift of the formula to the left of 8.8%. And an acceleration of the ESR of 52% was also revealed. In the study of biochemical blood analysis, hypoproteinemia (up to 65 g/l of protein) was determined 20% of C reactive protein was elevated in 23% of children with vitamin D deficiency. Thus, in conclusion, community-acquired pneumonia in young children is more severe in children with vitamin D deficiency and deficiency, have polymorphism of clinical symptoms of the disease. When making a diagnosis, pediatricians, general practitioners, and outpatient appointments should take into account the anatomical and physiological features of the respiratory organs in young children.

Conclusions. Vitamin D levels play an important role in the course, severity and adverse outcome of EAP in young children, which deserves special attention and requires a more in-depth

analysis in the diagnosis, prevention and treatment of diseases of the bronchopulmonary system. in children.

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